

How Can Students' English Speech Skill Be Improved?

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Abstract:

One of the most crucial language abilities is the ability to speak English, particularly in the business. However, speaking abilities are still relatively poor among students in general and pedagogy students in particular. The essay will give ideas to enhance the standard of teaching and learning in schools and will discuss the current state of English learning among students in an effort to at least partially address these inadequacies.

Keywords: *English Speech Skill, improve, language ability*

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Introduction

English has become a highly important tool in the contemporary integration setting; on the job market, a candidate with strong credentials and fluent English always makes a good impression on the employer. Candidates with strong English abilities have an advantage over those with comparable qualifications. The sad reality is that students' post-graduation English communication abilities, particularly speaking abilities, are still very subpar and do not satisfy employer needs. Recently, the media has also made numerous mentions of this circumstance. Even if pupils have grown up learning English, it is intriguing to observe why they fail to master the language. A thorough investigation is necessary to identify the primary contributor to this issue. The writer would like to boldly mention the reality of teaching and learning English in general, and the practice of speaking skills for students in particular, within the scope of the article that has been allowed, as well as the concerns of the teacher, and through It offers

some suggestions to help improve the quality of teaching and learning in schools.

Results and Discussion

The Current Situation of English Ability of Non-English Major Students

Many English-speaking students attend Tan Trao University. Approximately 70% of students have studied English for seven years or more, 26% have studied it for three years, and only about 4% of pupils do not know the language, according to some recent survey findings. However, the English questionnaires conducted at the start of the year reveal that pupils' understanding does not correspond to the quantity of English they have studied in high schools or at language immersion programs.

In English lessons, particularly during speaking practice sessions, very few students (only about 20–25%) are able to complete pair work and

group work tasks effectively. creative ideas flow easily.

The remainder simply practice in a stereotypical manner, frequently with the aid of prepared writings or dialogues (look at the ready-made material to read).

The majority of students' pronunciations (72%) are incorrect, and they particularly dislike the way they pronounce the last consonants.

The Current State of Non-English Major Students' English Learning

Learning motivation, learning attitude, and learning method are the three most crucial aspects that influence students' success in their academic endeavors.

Learning motivation

The term "motivation" has several various definitions. According to Harmer (1991), motivation is the internal drive that propels a person to pursue a course of action. We are motivated to accomplish a goal if we can see it and find it appealing enough.

Cole and Chan (1994) identified extrinsic and intrinsic motivation as the two key factors influencing learners' motivation to study. Factors beyond the classroom are referred to as extrinsic motivation. The allure of the community's culture that speaks that language is one of the variables outside of the classroom. Learners aspire to become assimilated into and learn about that culture. The necessity to utilize a foreign language as a second language to accomplish a given objective, like as applying for a job, earning more money, getting a promotion, etc., is another factor that exists outside of the classroom.

This external motivation is for Tan Trao University students to try to study English well in order to have the possibility to practice overseas, which is typically the case for Tan Trao University students. The author discovered during the actual teaching that once these pupils had such a strong incentive to learn, they outperformed their peers. The knowledge they have learned in school doesn't seem to be enough for them, therefore they constantly seek

out more difficult situations. This is also the reason that only a small number of students have enrolled in TOEIC, IELTS, or TOEFL preparation classes and made a statement.

A significant portion of students (54%) have also decided that their study goal is to be able to get a suitable career in the future, but their target was not realized owing to a number of subjective and objective circumstances.

Intrinsic motivation, as opposed to extrinsic drive, involves classroom-specific elements. This incentive is crucial in establishing students' learning attitudes, claim Cole and Chan (1994). Without intrinsic motivation, a student can still have a good attitude toward learning and do well in class. The four main factors that affect intrinsic motivation are as follows: first, the physical condition of the classroom, the teaching and learning materials, the environment, and the class size; second, the teaching approach, which is a deciding factor for students' interest in the subject; third, the teacher's personality, expertise, and enthusiasm, which are the factors that attract students to them; and fourth, the success or failure of the students themselves in learning.

The majority of students (64%) do not have the proper motivation to study, however, per the survey's findings. The elements that influence pupils' internal motivation are the basis of this issue:

- The physical state of the classrooms is not great: many classrooms are exposed to the heat (sunlight reaches half the class) in the summer; noise tolerance (for classrooms with corrugated iron roofs) in the rainy season...
- The lack of adequate teaching and learning tools prevents them from keeping up with the demand for new teaching techniques. The majority of English teachers at member schools use subpar cassette players, which has a significant impact on the quality of instruction.
- Class size: There are courses with too many students (45–65), which are inappropriate for foreign language classes and reduce the likelihood that students will practice their abilities.

- The majority of lessons are still taught using textbooks, chalk, and whiteboards.
- Students who perform poorly in school are less inclined to learn.

Learning attitude

The mindset of the students themselves is one aspect that has a significant impact on their achievement. According to Gardner and Lambert (1972), attitude is the tenacity with which students work to achieve a goal. In contrast, attitude, according to Brown (1980), is the perception that learners have of the community that uses that language and its culture. Learning motivation and learning attitude are closely related. A student's attitude toward learning a foreign language can inspire them to work hard to meet their objectives. In contrast, motivation influences how students feel. Externally or internally driven learners have a more positive attitude toward learning than unmotivated or mandatory learners.

At the Tan Trao University member institutions, 31% of students approach their English classes with a sense of being pressured and uneasy. They take English classes because it is a requirement for the program. Many Tan Trao students frequently adopt the mentality of learning to "cope" because there isn't adequate learning motivation: they use the answers provided in the textbook or steal them from earlier classes; They frequently do not concentrate during class, do not work well in groups with their companions, and when given an assignment, "beg" you or the teacher for assistance. Many students occasionally display a "non-cooperative" attitude, failing to prepare lessons beforehand, refusing to participate in class discussions, or making reasons to skip class or arrive late.

Learning Strategies

Strong students mostly rely on professors and can hardly manage on their own, in contrast to good students who can learn foreign languages quite well on their own.

Oxford (1990) defined learning strategies as specific actions that students do to make learning simpler, quicker, more pleasurable, and

more effective, as well as to make it easier for them to adjust to new situations.

Effective learning practices, according to O'Mally and Chamot (1990), involve planning learning, monitoring learning, and evaluating work produced. Knowing how to manage learning, such as taking notes, using dictionaries, and other resources, is another aspect of learning strategies. Additionally, it involves interacting with peers during group or individual communication tasks in class.

Students who wish to excel academically need the correct learning method in addition to the right learning motivation and good learning attitude. This is the reason why a lot of students love English and devote a lot of time to learning it, yet they still do not succeed in learning it.

In fact, examining how students learn English demonstrates that the majority of pupils lack an efficient learning strategy:

- Plan the lesson: Since students don't have the habit of thinking of ideas for speaking topics or circumstances in advance, they can't participate in class since they tend to focus on lexical meaning and disregard pronunciation and structure. meet the teacher's standards right away, but actual effectiveness isn't great.
- Vocabulary learning: Students frequently develop the practice of memorizing single words and repeatedly writing them down without developing the habit or understanding how to learn the word in context or in connection with other words. The efficiency with which words are retained through this method of learning is quite low. On the other hand, pupils struggle with both word usage and logical word arrangement.
- Communication activities in class: Communication activities in class are usually conducted by students as follows:
 - Get topic / situation
 - Giving ideas in Vietnamese
 - Translate ideas into English
 - Write ideas/dialogues on paper

- Look at a prepared dialogue or discussion to read.

Students must spend a lot of time in class planning and performing communication tasks in this manner, which reduces the available lecture time. Additionally, the kids' ability to think in English would suffer as a result of losing their agility and responsiveness.

In conclusion, learning strategy, motivation, and attitude all have a significant impact on both the general learning process and the development of students' speaking abilities. Students will have a good learning attitude when they are motivated to learn. They can then develop an efficient learning plan that produces excellent results for themselves. Students will become more enthusiastic, engaged in the subject, and have a better attitude toward learning once the desired results are obtained. Students will therefore make every effort to accomplish the objectives given.

Suggestions and Recommendations

For Teachers

- Pay more attention to students' motivation, attitudes, and learning tactics; assist students in accurately evaluating the value of English for their future so that they may pinpoint their own motivation, a pro-learning attitude, and successful learning techniques.
- Provide guidance and advice to students on how to prepare lessons, study vocabulary, apply new words to situations, learn how to pronounce, and use structure, arrange words, and arrange thoughts to make students feel more motivated to learn English.
- Don't make weak or slothful kids feel under pressure to study. Instead, promote independent learning among your students.
- Create various activity kinds that are appropriate for each group of kids and increase in difficulty.
- Create various activity kinds that are appropriate for each group of kids and increase in difficulty.

- Students are motivated to study because there is a fair reward and punishment system that gives them a foundation on which to gauge their level of effort and success.

- Evaluating pupils' genuine capacity to create appropriate standards; standards that are too low for good students will tire them and sap their motivation to improve; Too many demands will cause weak students to lose interest and their sense of self-worth.

- Encourage pupils to use Vietnamese in class only when necessary; restrict writing during speaking practice sessions.

- Foster communication confidence in kids; avoid overemphasizing proper grammar at the expense of instilling fear in them. Encourage kids to try to convey their ideas and thoughts instead.

For Students

- To enhance the quality of learning, choose for yourself the proper motivation, learning attitude, and learning approach.

- Modify the English-learning process to meet the demands of the times.

- Actively participate in class activities; limit writing assignments to what is absolutely essential; and use class time to practice speaking with peers.

- Always look for opportunities to speak with friends in English so that you can respond quickly.

- Develop the habit of thinking in English rather than translating concepts from Vietnamese into English.

- Speak clearly and with proper pronunciation. This is one of the elements affecting students' confidence.

For the School

- Focus more on teaching and learning tools to fulfill the demands of cutting-edge educational methodologies.

- Use small class numbers (30–35 students per class) to give pupils more chances to communicate with one another.

- Level-based class division will encourage pupils to speak up in class.

- - Arrange meetings with company leaders to give students the chance to hear what companies are looking for. This will help them focus their study.

Conclusion

It's not at all simple to improve the English-speaking abilities of students. The challenge is that it takes time to break an outdated foreign language study practice that isn't appropriate for the new circumstance. A substantial quantity of practice time and close collaboration between the teacher and the learner are also necessary for a skill to be perfected. The learners' own motivation, attitude, and learning techniques are far more crucial in determining success.

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